

Rainfall Manipulation Shelters for Agricultural Research

K. Kahmark, M. Jones, S. Bohm, N. Baker, and G.P. Robertson

W.K. Kellogg Biological Station, Michigan State University
January 2024

INTRODUCTION

This document covers the design, construction, irrigation, deployment, and instrumentation of rainfall manipulation shelters (Fig. 1) for controlling rainfall and establishing drought conditions in agricultural field research. Shelters are used to alter or manipulate rainfall and thereby create experimental footprints in agronomically active systems in order to investigate ecosystem resilience and examine the influence of environmental variability on ecosystem dynamics. These particular shelters are used in the [Main Cropping System Experiment \(MCSE\)](#) of the Kellogg Biological Station Long-term Ecological Research site (KBS LTER), and the Great Lakes Bioenergy Research Center (GLBRC)'s [Biofuel Cropping System Experiment \(BCSE\)](#) and [Marginal Land Experiment \(MLE\)](#).

Figure 1. Shelters deployed in a tilled cropping system and designed for proper drainage, irrigation, and overland flow protection.

Shelters cover 13.5 to 23.4 m² at a height suitable for row crops and short-statured herbaceous vegetation such as grasslands and early successional fields. Water can be captured by roof gutters and reapplied as irrigation water at defined intervals and rates, or can be brought in from off-site. Solar powered pumps feed low-pressure overhead sprinklers. Intrusion from overland flow is minimized with soil barriers and/or trenching. Wheels on corners allow shelters to be removed for agronomic activities. Roofing material is made of corrugated Lexan to allow for maximized PAR light penetration and channeling of rainwater. The design is rated for 145 km hr⁻¹ (90 mph) winds and a live snow load of 117 kg m⁻² (24 lbs ft⁻²) and light enough to be moved by 4 individuals.

Detailed instructions for shelter construction are included in Part 1 of this document; instructions for irrigation under the shelter are included in Part 2; deployment, instrumentation, and other shelter considerations are discussed in Part 3; and ancillary measurements are outlined in Part 4. Construction details are provided in English units to simplify materials purchase in the U.S.

PART 1: SHELTER CONSTRUCTION

Basic Materials

- 2" x 2", 14 gauge, square galvanized steel tube framing kit (67% recycled material – Versatube, Inc., USA)
- 18 gauge galvanized steel roof purlins (Versatube, Inc., USA)
- Clear Greca Lexan roofing (one-sided UV protection) (Amerilux, Inc., USA)
- Clear Lexan ridge cap (Amerilux, Inc., USA)
- Seamless 5" gutters, hangers, endcaps, and sealant
- ¾" straight bulkhead fitting (U.S. Plastics, USA PN 65478)
- Garden hose ¾" ID (Farmtek, USA)
- 1" #12 self-tapping roofing screws w/ grommet (Tek, Inc.)
- 4, 8" caster foam filled wheels (Caster Connections parts TP6680W-01-AFR and TP6680WR-01-AFR): two fixed and two swivel
- 2" #12 self-tapping roofing screws w/ grommet (Tek, Inc)
- 1" self-tapping screws (Versatube, Inc. USA)
- 10" Orange Screw ground anchors (<https://www.orangescrew.com/pages/ground-anchors>)
- 15" rubber strap with hooks
- Additional equipment as mentioned in text where appropriate

Tools

- Cordless drills with 5/16" hex socket drive
- Drill bit set
- Tape measure
- Deadblow hammer(s) 3 or 4 pound
- Markers
- Ladders (shelter height dependent)
- Level
- Safety glasses
- Work gloves

Preliminary Shelter Considerations

Desired study outcomes should be addressed before determining the shelter dimensions sufficient to answer study hypotheses. Shelter dimensions are based on the effective plot area needed underneath the shelter, maximum plant height, position in the landscape, type of vegetation (row crop vs. perennial), time of year installed, rainfall manipulation, regional weather/climate factors, local building codes, and labor force needed to deploy and conduct the study.

We found that a shelter frame with a common 3:12 roof pitch has a maximum width of 14' when constructed of 2" x 2" 14ga square galvanized steel. This frame dimension meets local snow live load and wind load (24 lbs/ft² and 90 mph, respectively) construction and safety codes. For frame widths larger than 14', engineering specifications call for using 2" x 3" steel which greatly increases the cost, weight, construction difficulties, and effort to intentionally move them in the field – requiring tractors with forklifts rather than people to move them.

Common 2" x 2", 14 ga steel frame shelter widths are 10', 12', and 14'. Common 2" x 3", 14 ga steel frame shelter widths are 16', 18', 20', 24', and 30'. The maximum and most common shelter width used at KBS research sites is 14', however 12' width shelters are also used in some drought/plant stress experiments. For shelter length decisions, consider under shelter plot size, typical weather patterns, and cost. There is more latitude in selecting shelter length than width because most of the stress is on the roof and truss width rather than length.

Select a construction site on reasonably level ground or a cement foundation. Although this construction type is very forgiving, the more level the surface, the more square the final shelter dimensions.

All parts from Versatube (<https://www.versatube.com/>) are shipped on large pallets. After arrival, check order carefully. A generic manual will be shipped with the order. Read through the manual. Versatube provides helpful diagrams and tips to make construction progress smoothly and safely. Follow all safety and hazard instructions provided.

Procedure

1. Review Fig. 2 for names of shelter frame parts.

Figure 2. Shelter nomenclature.

2. Lay out a set of base rails which will be equal to the desired length of your shelter. Base rails are commonly built on multiple 4' wide on-center frame sections with the addition of a 2' or greater wide extension to meet the desired shelter length. Our shelters are commonly 18' long; the final

length dimension is measured from the outside of the forward vertical side post base pin to the outside of the last vertical side post base pin. Each side consists of four base rails spaced at four-foot centers and a 2' extension base rail. It is possible to order one 8' base rail to substitute for two 4' base rails.

3. All square steel tubes have one swagged/bent and one female end; the swagged end fits snugly into the female end of the adjoining piece (Fig. 3). Parts should be tapped into place before fastening to each other. Fasten with two self-tapping screws offset from one another (see Fig. 3 lower panel).

Figure 3. Square steel tube connections

4. Each base rail has a horizontal section and a vertical base pin which will be used to fix the vertical side post/rafter assemblies to the base. After inserting one base rail piece into the adjoining piece, use two 1" -#12 self-tapping frame screws to attach. Screws should be slightly off center and diagonal from one another, and an inch or two apart (Fig. 3 lower panel). If the swagged fitting does not look like it is fully inserted, tap one rail while holding the second firmly before attaching with the screws. We advise selecting a high quality self-tapping screw.
5. After both base rail sides of a shelter are constructed, place them the approximate shelter width apart. Figure 4 shows a complete side assembly of an 18' long shelter after full construction. The base rails are horizontal, and the side posts are vertical.

Figure 4. Side assembly of an 18' long shelter

6. On the ground nearby, construct each roof rafter/vertical assembly. The center roof peak tubing section consists of a peak center piece and two rafter end pieces. The end pieces slide into each side of the peak center piece. This assembly looks like the gable end of a pitched roof, i.e., it is shaped like an inverted V. Then add the vertical side posts of desired height. There will be as many of these assemblies as there are vertical side post base pins on one complete base rail. For example, there are six of these assemblies in an 18' long shelter (Fig. 4). Once all rafter and side post assemblies are complete, add each to the base rail pairs as in the previous two figures and as explained in step 10. Figure 5 shows fully assembled rafter assemblies at two different stages in construction.

Figure 5. Rafter/vertical assemblies (12' x 12' shelter)

7. We recommend installing several type two collar truss assemblies to the shelter framing (Fig. 6) for further strength and support. This type of collar truss has three parts: a center tie and two end ties. The center tie has both ends swagged. Add an end tie to each side of the center tie, tap together, and attach to the center tie using two self-tapping screws slightly offset from one another.

Figure 6. Collar truss and vertical brace

8. The shelter framing should have a left and right collar truss bracket (Fig. 7) for each truss assembly. Attach one bracket to each end of the collar truss using several screws. Find a spot equidistant from the ends of each side post to each end of the collar truss to attach the bracket to the rafters. Use a screw pattern similar to the one in Figure 7. Place collar trusses on the first three rafter/vertical assemblies and one additional assembly (fourth or fifth). This lends strength to the shelter and allows a long tractor-mounted fork lift to pick up and move the shelter using the truss assemblies when necessary.

Figure 7. Collar truss bracket(s)

9. Connect one BK-30 bracket to each end of the included vertical brace (Fig. 8). Bracket tabs should face the same direction. Install the vertical brace from the center of the roof peak to the collar truss. This lends strength to the structure and allows the shelter to be raised and lowered using a tractor equipped with a long set of forks.

Figure 8. Vertical brace assembly with BK-30 brackets

10. Next, install the rafter/vertical frame sections to the base rails one at a time, moving sequentially down the base rails. (Fig. 9). Tap the top of the side post to make sure the frame sections are fully placed onto the base rail pins. Screw the rafter/vertical assembly to the base pin using at least four screws offset on each side.

Figure 9. Setting rafter/vertical section to the base

- Each side post should have a corresponding 18ga four hole eave corner bracket (Fig. 10). Bend the brackets to fit firmly along the curved portion of the side post. Bend the bracket so the vertical portion is flat to the side post as in Figure 10. Attach with two screws on each side of the bracket. This bracket allows the squaring of the curved section of the side post so the bottom purlins and roofing can be attached straight and firmly on the eave of the roof. It also serves as the site for gutter attachment on each shelter side.

Figure 10. Eave corner bracket assembly

- 18 ga galvanized steel purlins are provided in the “Versatube Grand style” design and serve as sites for roofing attachment. Purlins help to square the shelter because they attach one rafter/vertical assembly to another at several points along the roof pitch. Purlins are attached perpendicular to the rafter assemblies on approximately 3’3” spacings with three rows of purlins running parallel to each other on each side of the roof ridge, starting at the eave and working upward (Figs. 11 and 12). Self-tapping screws are used to fasten the purlins to the roof assembly (Fig. 12). During purlin installation, select an outer rafter/side post assembly corner bracket, and attach the purlin flush to the outer edge and at the lowest point of the roof pitch. Move horizontally to the next rafter

Figure 11. Purlins installation

Figure 12. Roofing overhang near gutter

assembly and screw in the first row of purlins so that the rafter spacing roughly matches the bottom of the vertical side post spacing. After the initial row, move up 3'3" and repeat with the next row of purlins. Repeat for a third and final row on one roof pitch. Then repeat this process on the opposite side of the shelter.

13. Next, attach the Amerilux clear Greca (square wave) Lexan (polycarbonate) roofing (<https://ameriluxinternational.com/our-products/corrugated-polycarbonate/>) to the shelter roof purlins. We use 50" W x 85.5" L sheets for 14' x 18' shelters and position them with a 2" overhang from the corner bracket over the gutter (Fig. 12) and a small gap at the peak. It is also important that the one-sided UV coating faces upward toward the sun to prevent yellowing of the polycarbonate.
14. Starting at one end of the roof, lay a sheet of Lexan parallel to the edge of the rafter assembly and attach to each purlin with #12- 1" self-tapping roofing screws with rubber/metal grommets. Check for roofing squareness to the frame as you move from one sheet to the next. Overlap the second sheet by two sheet troughs and similarly attach to the purlins. We use at least four screws across each sheet for each purlin.
15. The last sheet on each side of the roof should be cut to size so the panel edge is parallel and even with the edge of the roof framing (Fig. 13).

Figure 13. Roofing and ridge cap

16. Repeat the same process on the opposite side of the roof.
17. A polycarbonate ridge cap (Amerilux) is also installed and centered to protect the roof peak from water intrusion (Fig. 13). A foam spacer block can also be deployed between the ridge cap and the roofing sheets for added stability. See <https://ameriluxinternational.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/pdf-downloads/corrugated-polycarbonate/polycarbonate-ridgecap-install-guide.pdf> for installation. We forego the foam block to optimize air flow under the shelter roof.
18. Next, install a 5" inch seamless gutter with crimped end caps to the eaves of the shelter using gutter brackets on each side post (Fig. 14). Predrilling a hole just smaller than the bracket screw is helpful. The gutter should be installed with a sufficient drain slope, so that when deployed in the field, the user can effectively divert water away from the shelter footprint. An alternative is to finish this step

when the shelter is in place. We choose to minimize damage to field sites by installing gutters before deployment and adjusting the slope after deployment if necessary.

Figure 14. A 5" gutter with hangers

19. At the downslope edge, a $\frac{3}{4}$ " bulkhead fitting is installed on the bottom of the gutter after drilling the proper sized hole (Fig. 15). Once in place, we add an $\frac{3}{4}$ " ID industrial garden hose to drain runoff to an alleyway or acceptable area far enough away from the shelter so ponding does not occur nearby or under the shelter. If intense storms are predicted, the study may call for a larger ID bulkhead fitting and hose.

Figure 15. A $\frac{3}{4}$ " bulkhead fitting (gutter to drain hose)

20. A mobile field design is fundamental to our studies. Due to farm management practices that occur during the shelter deployment(s), our shelters need to be easily moved in and out of plots/treatments. To achieve this, we add two 8" fixed caster foam-filled wheels on the corner of each base rail furthest into the plot and two 8" rotating caster foam-filled wheels on the corner of

each base rail closest to the alleyway. This allows for easy movement and turning with two to four people when a forklift is not feasible. Caster wheels have a metal base with holes; use two u-bolts to attach each caster wheel to the base of the shelter (Fig. 16).

Figure 16. Caster wheel (swivel type)

21. Large 10" orange ground screws (<https://www.angescrew.com/products/large-ground-anchor-2-pack>) and 15" rubber straps are used to keep the shelters in place during heavy winds (Fig. 17).

Figure 17. Orange tie-down screw and strap

22. To maximize the treatment area under the shelter, side wall barriers that fill the area between the roof and the collar truss can be installed to help divert heavy rains away from underneath the shelter (Fig. 18).

Figure 18. Sidewall barrier for added protection

23. Modifications to this may be necessary for particular studies.

PART 2: IRRIGATION CONSTRUCTION

Basic Materials

- Irrigation sprinkler heads – Senninger Inverted Mini-Wobbler Nozzle Gold
- Polyethylene tubing ½" (0.600"ID x 0.700"OD)
- Irritec Perma-Loc Tubing End Cap - Perma-Loc Size: 1/2"
- Irritec Perma-Loc Tubing x FPT Tee Adapter - Perma-Loc Size: 1/2" - Thread Size: 1/2" FPT
- Global 1/2" MPT Poly Risers - Length: 6" or 12"
- Irritec Perma-Loc Tubing Coupling Valve - Size: 1/2"
- Schedule 40 PVC FPT Coupling - Size: 1/2 inch
- Irritec Perma-Loc Tubing Tee - Size: 1/2"
- Pump - (Seaflo Water Diaphragm Pump) 3Ga/min, 45PSI, diaphragm type
- Solar Controller- IP68 12V PWM Solar Controller or similar
- Battery - 32aH 12VDC AGM Sealed batteries
- Plastic Tote Box/Container
- 20W 12V Solar Panel
- 250 Gallon Tote Container (Used as Source Water Reservoir)

Procedure

At KBS, several rain manipulation studies that employ shelters require occasional waterings underneath the shelters to meet experimental objectives. Water must be from an acceptable water source. Some studies require an average weekly watering rate while other studies are more flexible or are under drought for prolonged periods. Tests should be conducted to check for desired "rainfall" coverage and amounts in the shelter footprint. The following is a protocol from just one of several designs used to irrigate footprint crops and soil during shelter deployments.

1. Determine the predominant wind direction in the study area. The areal position of sprinkler heads in the footprint varies due to wind direction, irrigation droplet size, and amount of “rainfall” added. In our studies, where the wind is primarily from the southwest, we add two sprinkler heads shifted slightly to the south for the best and most even coverage in the subplots under the shelter (Fig. 19).

Figure 19. Diagram showing the shift in subplot areas for further protection from heavy rainfall.

2. We use a 250-gallon tote container to store our water source and/or collect rainwater. The container is placed outside the footprint far enough to not diminish sunlight or disrupt airflow around the sheltered area (Fig. 20). Used containers are inexpensive, but be sure to thoroughly wash the inside of the container with a power washer and warm water if available. Tote containers are cleaned each season, sometimes several times per season, due to possible algal buildup. When totes collect rainfall, they can be covered with a tarp to prevent sun exposure and thus algal growth. In other studies, we fill the totes with either pond or groundwater 24 hours before irrigation. Characterizing the water used may be important. In a study at KBS, pH, inorganic nitrogen, cations, anions, and TOC were analyzed in local groundwater and compared to concentrations in rainwater before an appropriate water source was determined.

Figure 20. Tote containing water for under shelter irrigation.

3. We developed a mobile pump and power system that uses solar energy to transfer (pump) water from the tote container to the shelter footprint. The pump is located inside a plastic box and the solar panel is attached to the box lid; the assembly is placed on top of the tote container during use so the solar panel has full sun access. We utilize a 3 Gal/min, 45PSI, self-priming, diaphragm type pump with ½" NPT fittings, a HUINE 10A PWM Waterproof IP68 12V 24V Solar Panel Controller, 12V 32ah battery, on/off rocker switches, and wiring housed in the box with the 20W 12V monocrystalline solar panel fixed to the lid (Fig. 21).

Figure 21. Pump box position, interior setup, and solar panel

4. A weighted end section of ½" polyethylene tubing (.600" ID x .700" OD) is dropped to the bottom of the tote container. The other end of the tubing enters the power/pump box through a hole drilled in the side of the box and is connected to the incoming port of the pump using a union if necessary. Small holes are also drilled in the pump box bottom to allow water to drain if a leak occurs inside the box. Screen material is placed over the weighted polyethylene tubing to prevent uptake of material that may be in the irrigation source water.
5. Another section of tubing is connected to the pump outgoing port, routed through another hole in the pump box, and then hung appropriately on the shelter roof framing (Fig. 22). Tubing should be draped above the collar truss and attached to the roof purlins or framing where possible to prevent excessive dripping during irrigation. Connect irrigation tees in series at desired sprinkler locations and terminate at the last tee using a small portion of tubing and a plug. This helps in cleaning the lines when clogged with debris.

Figure 22. Irrigation plumbing from pump box to sprinkler

6. Use a plastic riser (or several) at each tee to set the sprinkler heads below the level of the collar truss and approximately one foot above the canopy. If set above the truss, the water from the sprinkler runs along the truss and soil coverage is uneven. Attach the tee to the vertical brace of the collar truss using two UV protected zip ties crossed diagonally at the tee. Then attach the riser to the vertical portion of the tee (Fig. 23). Sprinkler heads should have the ability to produce a droplet size similar to rainfall: too fine causes drift, too coarse makes it difficult to disperse water evenly throughout the footprint. An excessively large droplet size also causes a brief but strong rainfall which can damage crops or cause overland flow or erosion.
7. Once sprinkler heads are in place and the system is connected to a water source, test the system to determine the total water added to the sheltered footprint. Add a known amount of water to the tote container as in step 2. Run the sprinkler system until all water in the tote container is gone. Then, determine the outside of the shelter irrigated by the sprinkler system. Add this area to the shelter area to get the total area irrigated and determine the percentage area under the shelter. Assuming an equal distribution of irrigated water over the total area irrigated, multiply the total water in the container by the percent sheltered area to get the amount of water that fell in the shelter footprint.
8. As confirmation of the above calculation, when no crop is present, scatter an array of petri dishes throughout the footprint at the beginning of the above test. Measure the water volume collected in each dish (of known area) to calculate the total sprinkler water addition under the shelter. The rate of irrigation can also

Figure 23. Sprinkler head assembly.

be calculated by tracking the volume collected in the dishes over time. This is also an assessment of coverage uniformity.

9. This particular setup applies 150 gallons of water under a 14' x 18' shelter over three to four hours. Irrigation extends out from the sheltered area and must be accounted for in the total rainfall calculation desired, as discussed in Step 7.
10. The solar panel/controller can charge the 35aH battery within a day with clear skies, slightly longer with cloudy skies at the KBS latitude (Figs. 24 and 25).

Figure 24. Solar panel mounted on pump box lid.

Figure 25. Solar controller.

11. Solar power connections are as follows:
 - a. Connect battery to controller
 - b. Connect pump to controller
 - c. Connect solar panel
12. An on/off rocker switch installed in-line with the positive wire on the pump allows easy control of pump run time.
13. A union with an on/off valve in-line with the irrigation tubing helps keep debris and insects out of the irrigation system when the pump box is not connected (Fig. 26).

Figure 26. Irrigation union

PART 3: DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

Movement of Shelters

During the evolution of KBS rainfall shelter designs, it was clear that any design would need to provide easy access to sheltered areas during experimental sampling, shelter irrigation maintenance, and shelter repair. Additionally, agronomic activities in perennial and especially row crop agriculture do not cease once shelters are deployed, so efficient movement of shelters in and out of study plots was necessary. To achieve mobility, we developed a shelter frame that was rigid, but light enough to be moved by a few people. The addition of two sets of 8" foam-filled caster wheels at each shelter corner, one set fixed and one set swivel, allows researchers to move the shelters carefully and with relative ease. The shelter frame is strong and rigid enough to support a caster wheel on each corner without much weight stress. Four people can move these shelters across firm ground between row crops or in perennial systems with minimal, if any, crop damage. In a major study at KBS, four individuals, one on each shelter corner, could move 40 shelters out of plots (40' travel distance each) in a little over an hour in tilled, no-till, and perennial cropping systems.

At the start and end of each shelter field season, we use a John Deere 7420 tractor equipped with a long set of forks to move the shelters from and to their storage area, often several hundred meters from the study site. The fork system includes two 14' long solid forks (no extension) positioned eight feet apart. This allows the forks to capture at least three collar trusses and lift the unit safely and without dangerous sliding of the shelter. The fork system is also used to adjust shelter height. For example, in a corn season we first use a four foot vertical height. As the growing crop approaches the rafters, we use the fork system to easily and efficiently raise the shelter so additional side post section heights can be added by an experienced team (Fig. 27).

Figure 27. Shelter movement

Shelter Frame

Previous designs of rainfall manipulation shelters used PVC, wood, metal fence posts, or other materials for framing. For larger dimension shelters, such as 14' x 18', these materials are not suitable in the Midwest climate. Following local building codes would allow for increased confidence and success in shelter stability during extreme weather events. All shelter designs used for KBS research meet strict local garage

construction codes. The 2" x 2" galvanized square tube design and collar truss network, discussed in the construction section, allows for adequate protection from elevated or extreme snow loads and wind loads.

Using galvanized material prevents rust and provides longevity of the frame. Galvanized steel is cost efficient compared to aluminum or stainless steel and our shelter frame has a large percentage of recycled material. Seven-year-old shelters show no signs of structural fatigue or excessive rust.

The 3:12 roof pitch provides enough slope for rainfall to drain efficiently to the gutter system and flow away from the under-shelter area. Additionally, the frame roof pitch allows added protection from rainfall entering from the gabled sides of the shelter. A stronger, more pronounced pitch would mean more rainfall entry on the shelter ends.

Purlins run perpendicular to the roof frame and provide extra stability/rigidity and an adequate surface for properly securing the roofing to the frame. Purlins are of a lighter gauge material than the frame, so do not add significant weight to the structure. Weight savings are important for the manual movement of the shelter in the field and to minimize sinking of the wheels into the soil.

Plastic endcaps are available for installation for the open truss frame ends. Using these prevents wasps and other insects from taking up residence.

Shelter Height

KBS shelters are deployed in many different cropping systems, including wheat, soybean, corn, and switchgrass cropping systems; all are actively managed. Crop height and the crop's ability to intercept and minimize rainfall from intruding under shelter along the open shelter sides are important design considerations. It is advisable to determine the average maximum height of the studied crop and then choose a vertical side post height (including wheel height) that is approximately one foot greater than that to allow for irrigation if employed. For corn, we expect an average height at peak biomass in August of 8' and built the vertical side post to the height of 8'6" plus an 8" wheel height for a total of just over nine feet. However, if the shelter is built to this height just before field deployment early in the growing season when the crop is only a few inches tall, a moderate to heavy rainfall would likely result in water intrusion under the shelter plot area. To avoid this, we first install four-foot side posts, as discussed above. Then as the corn nears four feet, we add another four-foot section to allow accommodate its maximum height. This reduces exposure of the shelter footprint to potentially excessive rainfall intrusion. Four feet is also just above the maximum height for soybean and wheat; we use the same shelter for all cropping systems by adding/removing side post extensions.

Overland Flow Prevention

Shelters are constructed to either modify the amount of incoming rainfall under the shelter or to exclude rainfall from entering the soil footprint underneath the shelter. However, by themselves, shelters do not prevent overland flow of rain water into the sheltered footprint. Overland flow can be localized at the shelter perimeter and/or from further away and can occur at a velocity sufficient to cause rills or ponding. To prevent overland intrusion, several types of barriers and trenches may be installed.

For localized overland flow protection, consider installing either metal barriers or plastic edging into the soil just outside the footprint and shelter dimensions. Because shelters are often manually moved in and out of plots, the barrier material must be installed in a manner that does not obstruct shelter movement. In some cases, the barriers are removed and reinstalled after certain agronomic practices such as fertilization.

Prior to planting, observe the slope and direction of the land surrounding the shelter footprint including the overall plot slope. Then decide on how many upslope sides of the sheltered footprint area must be protected from possible surface flow. On some footprints, we add barrier edging around the entire shelter.

For sturdy barrier construction around the most vulnerable shelter footprints, Col-Met 8' by 4" metal powder-coated landscape edging is inserted 1" into the ground (Fig. 28). A battery powered lawn edger is used to make a starter slit in the soil. The barrier material is easily inserted and hammered or stacked into place in the sandy loam soils found at KBS. It is best to do this prior to or at crop emergence to limit plant damage around the footprint. If localized overland flow occurs near the footprint, the barrier diverts the flow around and downslope of the footprints.

Figure 28. Metal overland flow barrier

As an alternative, strong plastic edging can be installed with plastic anchoring spikes. An example is Easy-Flex no-dig 2.5" tall edging (Amazon). We invert the edging so the top can

be hammered slightly into the soil, then use the anchor spikes to hold it in place. This is a less expensive method and is effective for localized flow, but more difficult to install and not as sturdy as the metal barrier.

For a potentially greater and more aggressive overland flow that accumulates over longer distances, we create a trench around the sheltered footprint study area (Fig. 29). The trench is typically 10-15' upslope from multiple footprint areas. We use a walk behind trencher and travel in the direction that deposits the trenched spoils in the downslope direction, thus adding additional protection in the form of a berm. Surface flow will first be diverted around the study area via the 18+'' deep trench, and if the volume of water is

Figure 29. Protective trench and berm

excessive, the soil berm on the downslope edge of the trench will protect the study area from flow as well. Over the growing season the trench fills in with sediment and may need retrenching. This method is very effective.

Roofing Material and Light Transmittance

Rain exclusion shelter roofing must be a clear material that allows for maximum light transmission. To withstand field conditions, roofing material must also be durable against weather and lightweight enough not to impede intentional moving of shelters. Additionally, a rigid material, as opposed to flexible greenhouse film, adds stability to the shelter frame. KBS shelters are built using Amerilux clear Greca (square wave) Lexan (polycarbonate) roofing, which is clear, durable, lightweight, rigid, and corrugated, and provides effective channeling of rain to the gutter system.

The shelter gutters and frame block some light and cast shadows on crops (Fig. 30). Although the shelter roofing is clear, it also inhibits some sunlight from reaching the sheltered area. We use the Lexan clear corrugated roofing which has the highest light transmittance compared to other industrial clear plastic materials. New Lexan material allows 85-90% of light in photosynthetically active wavelengths to pass through and blocks light in the UV spectrum.

Figure 30. Shadows under the Lexan corrugated roofing material cast from the shelter frame and falling on an AccuPAR LP-80 ceptometer.

Glass roofing material would have higher light transmittance than Lexan roofing, but glass is too heavy, expensive, and breakable for KBS field projects. Additionally, the smooth surface of glass builds up dirt and sediment from rain droplets, while the corrugated surface of Lexan plastic allows water to more effectively drain off the shelter roof.

In order to characterize how the Lexan roofing material affects the light reaching sheltered crops, we measured the photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) under KBS shelters and under ambient field conditions with an AccuPAR LP-80 ceptometer (Decagon Devices, Inc., Pullman, WA). The LP-80 has 80 light sensors along an 84 cm long measurement bar and captures spatial light variation better than a point

measurement device. To find the percentage of total PAR transmitting through the shelter, we determined the average PAR under the shelter (from 15 locations in each repetition) and compared it to the average PAR under ambient conditions measured at the same time and height (from 4 locations in each repetition outside the shelter). We measured fewer locations under ambient conditions because there was little variation as compared to under the shelter, likely due to frame-cast shadows. Our PAR measurements were collected by holding the LP-80 level at waist height; preliminary measurements showed that measurement height below the roof did not have a significant effect on light transmission values.

This survey showed that at maximum solar radiation around midday, 2-year-old shelters transmit $71.4\% \pm 1.6$ of PAR on average. We also found that as shelters age, the percentage of light allowed to pass through the roofing decreases (Fig. 31), indicating that shelter roofing may need to be periodically replaced or cleaned to reduce the light-blocking effects. Overall, plants under shelters received less light than plants under ambient conditions. This could be a confounding experimental factor in projects using rain exclusion shelters, both in terms of less PAR reaching sheltered plants and potentially less drought stress due to reduced photosynthesis. Therefore, we recommend caution when making direct comparisons between ambient and sheltered crop data. However, comparisons between sheltered crops treated differently are scientifically defensible because they receive the same shelter impacts.

Figure 31. Percent transmission of light (in PAR range) through shelters of different ages. The “new” treatment is the value provided by Amerilux for the Lexan roofing after manufacturing.

PART 4: POTENTIAL ANCILLARY MEASUREMENTS

Soil moisture and temperature: Soil temperature is measured during each sampling campaign and in close proximity to the center of a portion of subplots under the shelter (Fig. 32). A Campbell Scientific CS650 soil moisture and temperature sensor is installed at an angle to provide an integrated depth of 25 cm. In some studies, we install two CS655 sensors horizontally at discrete 10 cm and 25 cm depths both under the shelter and in the ambient plot to track drought or rain water manipulations accurately. We also use a cross pattern of sensors under and just outside the shelter to understand potential rainfall intrusion and how much of a perimeter to include between the sheltered plot and the outside of the shelter. Soil temperature is measured at the surface interface via a thermistor in the main body of the sensor.

Air relative humidity and temperature: To examine the effect of shelters on relative humidity and temperature, we install a set of Campbell Scientific HygroVUE5 sensors in solar shields both under the shelter and outside the shelter area. Sensors are placed at similar heights above the canopy; those under the shelter are located just below the truss network to prevent erroneous readings from air in the rafter/truss region. We also deploy an Onset MX2302A RH/T logger and sensor units with matching solar shields if the shelter study has no access to Campbell Scientific data loggers or solar powered systems.

Data loggers: Campbell CS800 or CS1000 loggers are commonly used at KBS to collect most of our sensor data. The preference is to keep a network of similar logger systems in order to collect data most efficiently across many studies.

Meteorological data: Air temperature, relative humidity, precipitation, and atmospheric pressure should be recorded as close to the experimental site as possible. We annually evaluate light transmission through the roof by manually measuring and comparing PAR under and outside shelters on several sunny days using a Decagon LP-80 ceptometer. See the light transmittance section of this paper for further detail.

Biomass: Researchers measure annual net primary productivity (aboveground), percent canopy species composition along transects, phenology height, and other variables to examine changes in plant response. This list is not exhaustive.

GPS Coordinates: A REACH GPS unit is used to gather very accurate (cm-scale) footprint and subplot locations.

Soil Pore Water: METER SIC20 or similar porewater samplers are installed at one meter depth in several subplots in at least one major study at KBS.

Figure 32. Campbell Scientific sensor and greenhouse gas static chamber

Greenhouse gas emissions: Both static chamber (Fig. 32) and recirculation studies are common utilizing gas chromatography or laser spectroscopy measurements. Detailed protocols are available at <https://lter.kbs.msu.edu/protocols/113> and <https://lter.kbs.msu.edu/protocols/196>.

Acknowledgments: We thank the many technicians, students, and postdocs who helped during construction and implementation of various rainfall manipulation projects. We specifically thank Stacey Vanderwulp, David Weed, Carmella Vizza, and Joe Simmons for their efforts. We thank Jane Schuette for formatting and technical editing. Financial support was provided by the National Science Foundation Long-term Ecological Research Program (DEB 1832042), by the USDA Long-term Agroecosystem Research (LTAR) Program, by the Great Lakes Bioenergy Research Center, US Department of Energy, Office of Science, Office of Biological and Environmental Research (Award No. DE-SC0018409), and by Michigan State University AgBioResearch.